

2-TOM, 1-SON

Gimnastika zallardagi talablar va jihozlar

Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrulloevich

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti Jismoniy Madaniyat kafedrası o'qituvchisi

(Asian International University)

hikmatullosaefiyev@gmail.com

Anatatsiya: Gigienik talablar va foydalanish qoidalari sport zallari gimnastika bo'yicha o'quv mashg'ulotlari odatda maxsus jihozlangan gimnastika zallarida o'tkazilishi va ulardan foydalanish qonun qoidalari haqida keng manodagi ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'z: sport zal, jihoz, gimnastika tayoqchalari, to'plar, arqonlar, obruch, akrobatik mashqlar, arqon, bar, ko'prik, gimnastika paspaslari, akrobatik mashqlar uchun gilam, trambolin.

Gigienik talablar va foydalanish qoidalari sport zallari gimnastika bo'yicha o'quv mashg'ulotlari odatda maxsus jihozlangan gimnastika zallarida o'tkaziladi. Zallarda snaryadlar uchun yordamchi xonalar, o'qituvchi murabbiylar uchun xonalar, echinish xonalari (erkaklar, ayollar), shuningdek dush va hojatxonalar (hojatxonalar) kerak.

1. Zalni va uning yordamchi xonalarini bezatish tozalash uchun qulay bo'lishi kerak.

2. Isitish moslamalari panjara bilan qoplangan.

3. Zaldagi harorat 18-20 °C (namlik 50-60 %).

4. Shamollatish tabiiy va sun'iydir.

5. Derazalarning yorug'lik maydoni zamin maydonining kamida 1/5 qismidir.

6. Barcha xonalar muntazam ravishda tozalanishi kerak.

Jismoniy tarbiya zalida talabalarning o'zini tutish qoidalari

1. Gimnastika zaliga gimnastika kostyumida, o'qituvchi bilan, signal bilan, uyushgan holda kirish.

2. Mashg'ulotlar paytida o'qituvchining ko'rsatmalariga tezda rioya qiling, o'rtoqlariga yordam bering.

3. Snaryadga yaqinlashishdan oldin xavfsizlik qoidalarini bilib oling.

4. Zalda tozalikni kuzatib boring.

5. Ruxsatisiz zaldan chiqmang.

6. Uskunalar va jihozlarga ehtiyot bo'ling.

7. Darsni tugatgandan so'ng, ular uchun ko'rsatilgan joylarga snaryadlarni olib tashlang.

2-TOM, 1-SON

Gimnastika jihozlari

Gimnastika jihozlariga quyidagilar kiradi: gimnastika devori, gimnastika dastgohi, ot, echki, panjaralar, gimnastika jurnali, arqon, bar, ko'prik, gimnastika paspaslari, akrobatik mashqlar uchun gilam, trambolin.

Badiy gimnastika asboblari: gimnastika tayoqchalari, to'plar, arqonlar, obruch, akrobatik mashqlar.

Gimnastika mashg'ulotlarida shikastlanishning oldini olish

Gimnastika darslarida barcha choralar ko'rish kerak, xavfsizlik choralari rioya qilishga qaratilgan shikastlanishning oldini olish, ya'ni:

- har bir dars jadvali va rejasiga qat'iy rioya qiling;
- ishtirokchilarda ongli intizomni tarbiyalash, talab qilish ular barcha ko'rsatmalarni bajaradilar;
- har birining harakatlari ustidan doimiy nazoratni ta'minlash talaba, ularga bir turdan mustaqil ravishda o'tishni taqiqlang boshqasida ko'pkurash;
- talabalarni to'g'ri joylashtirish, yaxshi ta'minlash ko'rinish snaryadlar, itarish va qo'nish joylari. O'rnatish to'qnashuvlardan qochish uchun snaryadlar jalb qilingan.

Gimnastika mashg'ulotlarida sug'urta va yordam oldini olishga imkon beradi jarohatlar. Sug'urta deganda o'qituvchining tayyorligi yoki gimnastikachi quyidagi hollarda mashq bajaruvchisiga o'z vaqtida yordam beradi muvaffaqiyatsiz urinish. Sug'urtadan farqli o'laroq, yordam yordam beradi, traektoriya bo'yicha jalb qilinganlarni itarish, "simlar" u bajaradigan harakat. "Simlar" umuman harakatni o'zlashtirishni osonlashtiradi. Qo'llash "simlar", o'qituvchi faqat shunday jismoniy kuch sarflashi kerak, bu talabaning harakatlarini almashtirmaydi. Qisqa muddatli jismoniy yordam (surish) harakatning alohida bosqichlarini bajarish jarayonida paydo bo'ladi. Qo'llab-quvvatlash o'qituvchi tomonidan amalga oshiriladi boshlang'ich, oraliq va yakuniy pozitsiyalarda joylashgan, keyin, talaba hali yuk bo'lmagan vaqtida to'g'ri harakat qiladi.

Jismoniy tomondan mustaqil ravishda yordam va sug'urta minimal darajada, hal ustun ega o'z-o'zini sug'urtalashda. Jarohatlarning olish uchun so'rov orqali tavsiya qiling talabalar o'rganilayotgan texnika haqidagi bilimlarini bilib oladi haqida (bo'shatish momentlari snaryadlar, kengaytmalar va boshqalar). Buning sabablaridan biri unutmaz kerak ayollar umumiy va maxsus emas jarohat. Sinfda siz haddan tashqari sakrash bilan shug'ullanmasligingiz kerak va katta bo'lgan sakrash. Texnologiyani o'zlashtirish bilan bir qatorda gimnastika mashqlari bilan shug'ullanadilar, o'rganishlari

2-TOM, 1-SON

kerak o'qituvchi rahbariyati yordam va sug'urtani qabul qiladi. Boshida o'qituvchi sug'urta va yordam usullarini demonetizatsiya qiladi yangi elementni o'rganish jarayoni va kerakli narsalarni beradi ular. Keyin har bir talaba yordam uchun chaqiriladi yoki sug'urta, o'qituvchi esa ijrochini boshqasi bilan sug'urta qiladi tomonlar, bir tomondan o'zida sug'urta qilib tomosha qilish u o'z harakatni harakat. Talabaning yordam usullariga egaga ishonch hosil qilish va sug'urta, o'qituvchiga sheriklarini sug'urtalashni ishonib topshirishi mumkin, biroq, o'zi xato bo'lsa, yordam berish uchun yaqin ijrochiga. Faqat ko'rganni mustahkam o'zlashdan so'ng u talabalarga sug'urta va yordamni ularga ishonib topshirishi mumkin bir-biringizni mustaqil ravish sug'urta qiling.

Sport zallari va jihozlardan foydalanish qoidalari.

Sport zalida mashq qiladiganlar quyidagilarga rioya qilishlari kerak: qoidalar:

1) asbob-uskunalar va inventarlarni ehtiyotkorlik bilan, mohirona ishlatish ularni darslarga tayyorlang va keyin tozalang;

2) magniy bilan ehtiyotkorlik bilan va darslar oxirida ishlang amaliyotchilar shpalning barini, ustunlarini tozalashlari kerak magniydan barlar, halqalar, ot tutqichlari va bo'yralarni artib oling nam mato

3) zalda faqat sport kiyimi va poyabzalda bo'lish;

4) dars paytida o'qituvchining ko'rsatmalariga qat'iy rioya qilish (murabbiy), o'rtoqlarga yordam bering;

5) xavfsizlik qoidalarini, o'zini o'zi sug'urta qilish texnikasini o'rganish;

6) zalga kirish va chiqish faqat ruxsatnoma bilan mumkin o'qituvchi. Har kuni tekshirish tavsiya etiladi gimnastika jihozlari va topilgan muammolarni darhol hal qiling. Oyda bir marta jihozlarni yanada to'liq tekshirishni o'tkazish kerak.

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